

International Large-Scale Assessments of Mathematics Achievement in Ireland

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During the last few decades, international large-scale assessments of student achievement have attracted a lot of attention from educational stakeholders worldwide due to the quantity and quality of the information they provide, and Ireland is no exception. Results of both PISA and TIMSS across years have shown that Irish students perform consistently well on average in mathematics, however, some elements of their achievement have been a matter of concern. In this paper, areas of mathematics assessed by international assessments, strengths and weaknesses of Irish students' mathematics achievement, and potential policy directions to address some identified issues are discussed.

Keywords: international assessments; PISA; TIMSS; mathematical literacy

The predecessor of contemporary international large-scale assessments of student achievement and the first of its kind, conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in 12 countries between 1961 and 1965, is the First International Mathematics Study (FIMS). FIMS assessed 13-year-old students and its primary aim was to compare student outcomes across education systems (Mullis & Martin, 2006). Having mathematics as the assessment domain of the first international study was based on a number of reasons, including the universal value of the subject and its importance for progress in other subjects, the commonalities of mathematics curricula across countries, and the nature of the subject that allows for easier translation of the questions compared to other subjects where longer texts are used (Mullis & Martin, 2006). FIMS established the feasibility of international assessments across linguistically and culturally different contexts.

Ireland did not participate in FIMS. Ireland's first participation in an international assessment was in 1971 (in the civic education component of the Six Subjects Study), and despite that, it was not until the late 1980s to early 1990s that Ireland began to regularly participate in international assessments. Since then, mathematics achievement, alongside achievement in other subjects, has been assessed across different international assessments and student cohorts at both primary and post-primary levels. At the time of writing, mathematics achievement of Irish students has been assessed in all eight cycles of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (starting in 2000), and five cycles of the IEA's Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) (starting in 1995).

PISA assesses the knowledge and skills of 15-year-old students worldwide, but it is not a curriculum-based assessment – it assesses student performance on “real-life” tasks that are considered relevant for effective participation in adult society and for life-long learning (OECD, 2021). In the most recent cycle of PISA, mathematical literacy is defined as

an individual's capacity to reason mathematically and to formulate, employ, and interpret mathematics to solve problems in a variety of real-world contexts. It includes concepts, procedures, facts and tools to describe, explain and predict phenomena. It assists individuals to know the role that mathematics plays in the world and to make the well-founded judgments and decisions needed by constructive, engaged and reflective 21st century citizens (OECD, 2018, p. 7)

The PISA mathematics domain comprises four content areas: (i) change and relationships, (ii) space and shape, (iii) quantity, and (iv) uncertainty and data, three cognitive processes: (i) formulate, (ii) employ, and (iii) interpret and evaluate, and four contexts: (i) personal, (ii) occupational, (iii) societal, (iv) scientific.

TIMSS is a curriculum-based assessment at grades 4 and 8 (corresponding to Fourth Class and Second Year in Ireland) and, in the most recent TIMSS cycle, its mathematics framework is organised around two dimensions: content, specifying the subject matter domains to be assessed (i.e., number, algebra, geometry and measurement, data and probability), and cognitive, specifying the thinking processes to be assessed (i.e., knowing, applying, reasoning) (Mullis et al., 2021).

Results of both PISA and TIMSS across years have shown that Irish students perform consistently well on average in mathematics (with the exception of PISA 2009, where a significant performance decline was noted) (McKeown et al., 2019; Perkins & Clerkin, 2020). However, while lower-achieving students have done relatively well in both assessments, the lower-than-expected performance and the relatively low proportions of higher-achieving students, especially at post-primary level, have been a matter of concern (Pitsia, 2021).

To help interpret what students' scores mean in substantive terms, the PISA and TIMSS performance scales are divided into proficiency levels or benchmarks that indicate the kinds of tasks that students whose scores are above a lower score limit are capable of completing successfully. These six proficiency levels and four benchmarks in PISA and TIMSS, respectively, are accompanied by descriptions of the skills and knowledge that students are able to demonstrate. Students performing at proficiency levels 5 and 6 in PISA and at the advanced international benchmark in TIMSS are usually considered to be the high-achieving students in a given subject. In PISA mathematics, students at proficiency level 5 "can develop and work with models for complex situations ... [and] work strategically using broad, well-developed thinking and reasoning skills, appropriate linked representations, symbolic and formal characterisations, and insight pertaining to these situations" (OECD, 2019, p. 105); while students at proficiency level 6 "can conceptualise, generalise and utilise information based on their investigations and modelling of complex problem situations, and can use their knowledge in relatively non-standard contexts Students at this level can [also] reflect on their actions, and can formulate and precisely communicate their actions and reflections ..." (OECD, 2019, p. 105).

In TIMSS mathematics, grade 4 students performing at the advanced international benchmark "... can solve a variety of multistep word problems involving whole numbers and show an understanding of fractions and decimals ... apply knowledge of two- and three-dimensional shapes in a variety of situations ... [and] interpret and represent data to solve

multistep problems” (Mullis et al., 2020, p. 36), while grade 8 students at the advanced international benchmark “can apply and reason in a variety of problem situations” such as algebraic, geometric, statistical, and probabilistic problems (Mullis et al., 2020, p. 173).

The relatively low proportions of students (especially at post-primary level) demonstrating these kinds of advanced skills and knowledge in mathematics across all cycles of PISA and TIMSS (ranging mostly between 7% and 10%), along with the performance decline in PISA 2009 prompted the formulation and implementation of a number of policies and initiatives and new strands of research over the last fifteen years in Ireland. The development of curricula for Junior Cycle mathematics, including Project Maths that was implemented on a phased basis between 2008 and 2015 (e.g., Kirwan, 2015), the National Strategy to Improve Literacy and Numeracy among primary and post-primary students introduced in 2011 (Department of Education and Skills, 2011), constituting the first governmental policy document that established nation-wide targets concerning high achievement in mathematics at primary and post-primary levels and its interim report (Department of Education and Skills, 2017a), the bonus points scheme introduced in 2012 (Central Applications Office, 2012), the establishment of the STEM Education Review Group in 2013 (The STEM Education Review Group, 2016), and the Policy Statement on STEM education 2017-2026 (Department of Education and Skills, 2017b) all emerged to a great extent as a response to Ireland’s results in international large-scale assessments, establishing these assessments as official indicators of Irish student performance and emphasising their key role in Irish educational policy-making. As noted by Harold Hislop, former Chief Inspector in the Department of Education, “the public and political interest aroused by PISA ... deepened ... interest in how well students are learning ... and [led to] a commitment to tackling long-standing issues” (Hislop, 2011, p. 7).

The heightened focus of national policy and research on the results of international large-scale assessments, although crucial for driving change, is not sufficient on its own. Focusing on the impact of these results, and the associated policies, on teaching and learning is key. An important step going forward would be to strengthen the links of policy and research with practice in schools to be able to move from the contemporary practice, which, at post-primary level, is heavily focused on the teaching of the knowledge and skills students need to perform well on the state examinations, to the policy aspiration, which is raising the proportions of students with strong mathematical knowledge and skills, and improving the performance of existing high-achieving students.

References

Central Applications Office. (2012). *Bonus points for Higher Level Leaving Certificate Mathematics*. Central Applications Office.
http://www2.cao.ie/otherinfo/calc_points.pdf

Department of Education and Skills. (2011). *Literacy and Numeracy for Learning and Life: The national strategy to improve literacy and numeracy among children and young people 2011-2020*. Department of Education and Skills.

Department of Education and Skills. (2017a). *National Strategy: Literacy and Numeracy for Learning and Life 2011-2020 - Interim review: 2011-2016. New targets: 2017-2020*. Department of Education and Skills.

Department of Education and Skills. (2017b). *STEM Education: Policy statement 2017-2026*. Department of Education and Skills.

Hislop, H. (2011). *Teacher education and Ireland's National Strategy to Improve Literacy and Numeracy*. SCOTENS Annual Conference.

Kirwan, L. (2015). Mathematics curriculum in Ireland: The influence of PISA on the development of Project Maths. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 8(2), 317–332.

McKeown, C., Denner, S., McAteer, S., Shiel, G., & O'Keeffe, L. (2019). *Learning for the future: The performance of 15-year-olds in Ireland on reading literacy, science and mathematics in PISA 2018*. Educational Research Centre.

Mullis, I. V. S., & Martin, M. O. (2006). *TIMSS in perspective: Lessons learned from IEA's four decades on international mathematics assessments*. TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education, Boston College.

Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., Kelly, D. L., & Fishbein, B. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 international results in mathematics and science*. TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education and Human Development, Boston College, and International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA).

Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., & von Davier, M. (Eds.). (2021). *TIMSS 2023 assessment frameworks*. TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Lynch School of Education and Human Development, Boston College, and International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA).

OECD. (2018). *PISA 2021 mathematics framework (draft)*. PISA, OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/sitedocument/PISA-2021-mathematics-framework.pdf>

OECD. (2019). *PISA 2018 results (Volume I): What students know and can do*. PISA, OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>

OECD. (2021). *PISA 2018 technical report*. PISA, OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/data/pisa2018technicalreport/>

Perkins, R., & Clerkin, A. (2020). *TIMSS 2019 Ireland's results in mathematics and science*. Educational Research Centre.

Pitsia, V. (2021). *Investigating high achievement in mathematics and science in Ireland: An in-depth analysis of national and international assessment data* [Dublin City University]. <http://doras.dcu.ie/25255/>

The STEM Education Review Group. (2016). *STEM Education in the Irish school system - A report on science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) education: Analysis and recommendations*. The STEM Education Review Group.